
D5.3 / Report on the status of posting results (dBM-DEV study)

Editor	Contractual delivery	Actual delivery
Björn Falkenburger (TUD)	September 2025	March 2026
Deliverable type	Dissemination level	Version - date
R - Document, report	PU – Public	1.0 – 04/03/2026

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Deliverable ID

Project acronym	AI-PROGNOSIS
Project full title	Artificial intelligence-based Parkinson's disease risk assessment and prognosis
Grant Agreement ID	101080581
Deliverable number	D5.3
Deliverable title	Report on the status of posting results (dBM-DEV study)
Work package	WP5 – Clinical studies
Deliverable type	R - Document, report
Dissemination level	PU – Public
Version - date	0.1 - 04/03/2026
Contractual delivery	September 2025
Actual delivery	March 2026
Lead partner	TUD
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Keywords	Accelerometer; Active test; Balance; Bradykinesia; Clinical study; Cognition; Daytime somnolence; Digital biomarkers; Dyskinesias; Ethics approval; Gait; Heart activity; Parkinson's disease; Posture; REM-sleep behaviour disorder; Resting tremor; Smartphone; Smartwatch; Study protocol

Document history

Version	Date	Contributors	Action / status
0.1	09/09/2025	TUD	Document structure (table of contents) ready
0.2	30/10/2025	TUD	Revised document structure
0.3	08/01/2026	TUD, AUTH, CERTH, KUL, INTRA, CHUT, FIN, Abbvie	Completed information
0.4	09/02/2026	TUD, AUTH	Minor edits; Ready for internal review
0.4	24/02/2026	CING	Reviewed by Paraskevi Chairta
0.4	24/02/2026	AING	Reviewed by Ali Saad
0.5	25/02/2026	TUD	Document revised
0.6	02/03/2026	TUD, ABBV, AUTH, CHUT	Additional checks and revisions after quality checks
0.7	04/03/2026	AUTH, ABBV, TUD	Minor edits and revisions; Approved by the Project Coordinator for submission
1.0	04/03/2026	AUTH	Submitted version

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List of abbreviations

(i)RBD	(idiopathic) REM sleep behaviour disorder
AI-PMP	AI-based Progression and Medication response Prediction study
BART	Balloon Analog Risk Task
CAPA	Corrective and Preventive Action
CERTH	Centre for Research and Technology Hellas
CHUT	Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Toulouse
CMFT	Comprehensive Motor Function Test
dBM	Digital biomarker
dBM-DEV	Digital Biomarkers Development Study
eCRF	Electronic Case Report Form
ESS	Epworth Sleepiness Scale
FIN	Fundacion Iniciative para las Neurociencias
FPS	Frames per second
ICC	Intraclass correlation
IRB	Institutional Review Board (or Ethics Committee)
KCL	King's College London
LRS	Levodopa Response Study
MDS-UPDRS	Movement Disorders Society-sponsored revision of the Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale
MJFF	Michael J. Fox Foundation
MoCA	Montreal Cognitive Assessment
n.s.	Not significant(ly)
PD	Parkinson's disease
PDQ-8	Parkinson's disease questionnaire, 8-item version
PSG	Polysomnography
RBDSQ	REM sleep behaviour disorder screening questionnaire
REM	Rapid eye movements
TUD	Technische Universität Dresden

Executive summary

This deliverable reports on the results of the Digital Biomarkers Development Study (dBM-DEV study) (NCT06444789). The aim of the dBM-DEV study was to develop and assess the feasibility and validity of smartwatch-based digital biomarkers (dBM) and mobile app-based user active tests for different motor and non-motor symptoms of Parkinson's disease (PD). The primary objective was to develop smartwatch-based digital biomarkers for Rapid Eye Movement Sleep Behaviour Disorders (RBD) using data from a development cohort and external datasets, and to assess their validity in a confirmation cohort. Fifty-three (53) participants were enrolled in the development cohort [24 controls, 27 with idiopathic RBD (iRBD), 2 with RBD and PD] and 28 participants in the confirmation cohort, all with PD.

The primary study end point was the specificity of the dBM for RBD in comparison to the standardised RBD Screening Questionnaire (RBDSQ), with polysomnography-confirmed RBD as the ground truth. The analysis for the primary end point was inconclusive because the number of participants in the confirmation cohort without RBD (negatives) was eventually too low. Results of this study will be used to adequately address this issue in future research.

Five out of seven secondary endpoints and four out of five exploratory endpoints were positive. Positive secondary endpoints include the feasibility of smartwatch-based dBM for bradykinesia, dyskinesias, and rest tremor, cognitive active tests, and for touchscreen typing-based assessment of fine movement. Positive exploratory endpoints include significant correlation of the smartwatch-based dBM for rest tremor and slowness of gross movements of the upper extremities, as well as of the typing-based assessment of fine movement with the corresponding Movement Disorders Society-sponsored revision of the Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale (MDS-UPDRS) clinical scores.

Results will be posted to the registry where the clinical study was registered (clinicaltrials.gov, NCT06444789) at the latest by the end of the project. Data monitoring and analysis will continue beyond February 2026.

1 Introduction

1.1 Document scope

This deliverable reports on the results of the Digital Biomarkers Development Study (dBM-DEV study). The aim of the dBM-DEV study was to develop and assess the feasibility and validity of smartwatch-based digital biomarkers (dBM) and mobile app-based user active tests for different motor and non-motor symptoms of Parkinson's disease (PD). The report reflects the status of analysis by February 2026. Results will be posted to the registry where the clinical study was registered (clinicaltrials.gov, NCT06444789) as soon as analyses are completed, at the latest by the end of the project.

1.2 Document structure

The document is structured as follows:

- Section 2 reports on study protocol revisions and ethical approval (update from D5.2 "Report on the status of posting results (dBM-DEV study)")
- Section 3 reports on study enrolment and participant characteristics
- Section 4 reports on the status of the analysis of study endpoints
- Section 5 reports on the ethical and personal data protection compliance
- Section 6 summarizes the key findings and provides an outlook on next steps.
- Section 7 concludes the report

In addition, the following documents are collated as appendices:

- S.1: The most recent protocol version (1.5), which includes a list of changes implemented in each revision.
- S.2 Approval letter for amendment at clinical site FIN.
- S.3 Approval letter for amendment at clinical site CHUT.
- S.4: Study Data Management Plan (study DMP)
- S.5: Documentation of Corrective and Preventive Action (CAPA)

2 Protocol revisions and ethical approval

To accommodate ongoing refinements, the study protocol has been continually adapted as detailed in **Table 1**. The latest protocol (version 1.5) is attached as supplementary document S.1, alongside approval decisions of latest amendments (S.2, S.3).

Table 1 Protocol versions currently in use at each study site, along with the approval dates

Study site	Active protocol version	Approval date
TUD	1.5	04 April 2025
CHUT	2.0*	27 Aug 2025
FIN	1.5	07 Jan 2026

*Corresponds to 1.5 in other sites.

3 Enrolment and patient characteristics

The dBM-DEV study aimed to enrol 90 participants in two (2) cohorts at four (4) clinical sites. During study initiation, the King's College London (KCL) site was discontinued. Consequently, the enrolment of participants had to be redistributed among the remaining study sites (i.e., Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Toulouse (CHUT), France; Fundacion Iniciativa para las Neurociencias (FIN), Spain and study lead Technische Universität Dresden (TUD), Germany). Participants wore a smartwatch and used the AI-PROGNOSIS mAI-Health app to collect data, perform the active motor function and cognitive tests, and report each morning the occurrence of Rapid Eye Movement Sleep Behaviour Disorders (RBD) episodes during the previous night. Data were automatically transmitted to a Cloud-based study database.

The primary objective was to develop smartwatch-based digital biomarkers for RBD, using data from a development cohort and external datasets, and to assess their feasibility and validity in a confirmation cohort. The analysis of the primary study end point was the specificity of the dBM for RBD in comparison to the standardised RBD Screening Questionnaire (RBDSQ), with polysomnography (PSG)-confirmed RBD as the ground truth.

Despite the anticipated obstacles posed in the dBM-DEV study due to the aforementioned recruitment redistribution, a sufficient number of 81 participants was finally enrolled in the dBM-DEV study, with 53 participants in the development cohort (24 controls, 27 with idiopathic RBD (iRBD), 2 with RBD and PD) and 28 participants in the confirmation cohort, all persons with PD. The planned and actual enrolment of study participants per cohort and site is shown in **Figure 1**. Study participants were between 47 and 83 years old and from diverse backgrounds. The impact of the lower number of study participants, 81 recruited versus 90 planned overall and 28 recruited versus 30 planned participants in the confirmation cohort) is discussed below.

Figure 1 Planned and actual enrolment of study participants per cohort and site.

Patient characteristics (age, sex, height, weight) and clinical data were collected through electronic case report forms (eCRFs) implemented in the OpenClinica clinical study data

management platform. These characteristics include scores of rating scales for sleepiness (Epworth Sleepiness Scale, ESS), cognitive performance (Montreal Cognitive Assessment, MoCA), the likelihood of REM sleep behaviour disorder as reported by a questionnaire (RBDSQ), the severity of PD motor symptoms (Movement Disorders Society-sponsored revision of the Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale, MDS-UPDRS) and health-related quality of life (PD questionnaire, 8-item version, PDQ-8). Confirmation cohort participants would undergo a single PSG study in a sleep laboratory. **Table 2-Table 4** summarise the status of data for the two cohorts of the dBM-DEV study in February 2026. Education levels are based on the ISCED 2011 Levels of education¹.

Collection of certain variables, such as height, weight, ethnicity, race, and area of residence were added in an amendment after study initiation. and are therefore not available for all participants. The consortium is currently preparing amendments to the study protocol to obtain these missing data. Data monitoring will continue beyond February 2026 as outlined in the collated study DMP (S.4) and Corrective and Preventive Action (CAPA) (S.5) documents. .

Table 2 Summary of patient characteristics and clinical data in the development cohort for participants with RBD; y/n: yes/no.

Information	Number of participants with data	Median	Range
Age (years)	29	72.0	54.0-83.0
Height (cm)	18	170	158-184
Weight (kg)	18	74.0	53.0-105.0
Education (level)	29	4.0	1.0-8.0
ESS score	28	8.0	1.0-18.0
MoCA score	21	28.0	23.0-30.0
RBDSQ score	29	9.0	4.0-12.0
MDS-UPDRS score	29	10.0	0.0-72.0
PDQ-8 score	29	2.0	0.0-22.0
Information	Number of participants with data	Option A	Option B
Sex (male/female)	29	6	23
Handedness (right/left)	29	28	1
Ethnicity (Non-Hispanic/Hispanic)	21	17	4
Race (white/other)	21	21	0
Residence (village/town or city)	21	2	19
Participant has PD (y/n)	29	2	27
Nights with/without RBD as reported by caregiver	24	8	3-30
PSG available (y/n)*	29	7	22

* Two participants with RBD of the development cohort per clinical site would undergo PSG recording.

¹ ISCED 2011 Levels of education - [https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=International_Standard_Classification_of_Education_\(ISCED\)](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=International_Standard_Classification_of_Education_(ISCED))

Table 3 Summary of patient characteristics and clinical data in the development cohort for participants without RBD (controls); y/n: yes/no.

Information	Number of participants with data	Median	Range
Age (years)	24	66.5	47.0-81.0
Height (cm)	18	172	155-183
Weight (kg)	18	76.5	47.0-93.0
Education (level)	24	6.0	2.0-8.0
ESS score	24	4.0	0.0-13.0
RBDSQ score	24	0.0	0.0-6.0
MDS-UPDRS score	23	2.0	0.0-9.0
PDQ-8 score	24	0.0	0.0-8.0
Information	Number of participants with data	Option A	Option B
Sex (male/female)	24	16	8
Handedness (right/left)	24	22	2
Ethnicity (Caucasian/Hispanic)	17	12	5
Race (white/other)	17	17	0
Residence (village/town or city)	17	2	15

Table 4 Summary of patient characteristics and clinical data in the confirmation cohort (participants with PD and unknown RBD status); y/n: yes/no.

Information	Number of participants with data	Median	Range
Age (years)	28	62.5	50.0-77.0
Height (cm)	25	170	152-187
Weight (kg)	25	74.0	47.0-172.0
Education (level)	28	6.0	2.0-8.0
Disease duration (years)	28	5.0	1.0-16.0
ESS score	28	7.0	2.0-14.0
MoCA score	28	28.0	24.0-30.0
RBDSQ score	28	8.0	3.0-13.0
MDS-UPDRS score	28	35.5	20.0-89.0
PDQ-8 score	28	6.0	0.0-18.0
Information	Number of participants with data	Option A	Option B

Sex (male/female)	28	13	15
Handedness (right/left)	28	24	4
Ethnicity (Caucasian/Hispanic)	21	12	9
Race (white/other)	21	21	0
Residence (village/town or city)	21	21	0
PD subtype (tremor/other)	25	16	9
PD dominant side (right/left)	25	13	12
PSG data			
Information	Number of participants with data	Option A	Option B
PSG conclusive (y/n)	24	16	8
RBD detected in conclusive PSG (y/n)	16	13	3
Smartwatch data during PSG (y/n)	26	23	3
RBD identified by developed dBM (y/n)	23	22	1

4 Analyses of study endpoints

In this section, we present the data gathered in the dBM-DEV study as well as the analyses for the primary, secondary, and exploratory endpoints. Details on material and methods for the development of the dBM mentioned, alongside detailed results not limited to the dBM-DEV study data, are provided in the AI-PROGNOSIS public deliverable D3.3 “Final report on digital biomarkers for PD”.

4.1 Primary endpoint - Specificity of dBM for RBD

The primary aim of the dBM-DEV study was to quantify the incidence of nights in a confirmation cohort in which RBD episodes are indicated by dBM derived from passive actigraphy and photoplethysmography data captured by a smartwatch the participant wore during sleeping.

4.1.1 Study results

The development of the dBM for RBD is described in D3.3. In brief, features associated with night-time mobility were extracted from accelerometry data and a machine learning model was trained to classify the night as with or without RBD. **Table 5-Table 7** summarize certain of these features in the two cohorts of the dBM-DEV study.

Table 5 Features associated with RBD in participants of the development cohort for participants with RBD.

Information	median	range	Number of participants
Fraction of Medium- Duration Movement Event	0.19	[0.00, 0.31]	28

Amplitude Peak Median of Movement Event (g)	1.19	[0.79, 1.33]	28
Amplitude Peak Mean of Movement Event (g)	1.29	[0.82, 1.51]	28
Duration Median of Movement Event (s)	0.59	[0.12, 1.83]	28
Duration Mean of Movement Event (s)	1.44	[0.41, 3.07]	28

Table 6 Features associated with RBD in participants of the development cohort for participants without RBD (controls).

Information	median	range	Number of participants
Fraction of Medium Durations of Movement Event	0.27	[0.17, 0.35]	22
Amplitude Peak Median of Movement Event (g)	1.26	[1.19, 1.39]	22
Amplitude Peak Mean of Movement Event (g)	1.40	[1.27, 1.53]	22
Duration Median of Movement Event (s)	0.93	[0.69, 1.78]	22
Duration Mean of Movement Event (s)	1.93	[1.39, 2.99]	22

Table 7 Features associated with RBD in participants of the confirmation cohort.

Information	median	range	Number of participants
Fraction of Medium Durations of Movement Event	0.16	[6.98,24.55]	28
Amplitude Peak Median of Movement Event (g)	1.16	[0.89, 1.45]	28
Amplitude Peak Mean of Movement Event (g)	1.24	[0.92, 1.75]	28
Duration Median of Movement Event (s)	0.47	[0.16, 1.75]	28
Duration Mean of Movement Event (s)	1.20	[0.52, 2.56]	28

Out of the 26 participants with dBM's data in the confirmation cohort, three (3) participants were excluded from the analysis because fewer than seven days of accelerometry data were available. The dBM's for RBD were predicted to be positive in 22 participants and negative in 1 participant.

As mentioned above, 24 PD patients from the confirmation cohort underwent one night of PSG; PSG was delayed in 2 participants. Thirteen (13) PSGs were RBD-positive, three (3) were negative, while four (4) PSGs nights yielded insufficient sleep for a reliable analysis and four (4) were classified as suspected RBD but not confirmed.

4.1.2 Analysis of results

As described in the protocol, the main evaluation criterion for the dBM-DEV study was defined as follows:

The Primary endpoint would be considered positive if:

- (i) RBD-associated features were observed in all participants with RBDSQ > 6 and PSG-confirmed RBD,
- (ii) no RBD-associated features were observed in participants with RBDSQ < 6 and no PSG-confirmed RBD, and
- (iii) no RBD-associated features were observed in at least 40% of participants with RBDSQ > 6 but no PSG-confirmed RBD.

This definition was based on assumptions about the prevalence of RBD in PD and about the sensitivity and specificity of the RBDSQ. These assumptions are summarized in **Table 8** along with the results.

Table 8 Assumptions and results regarding prevalence of RBD as defined by PSG, RBD dBM and RBDSQ; ¹participant did not sleep or RBD was suspected but not confirmed; ²secondary outcome, not significantly (n.s.) different from questionnaire ($p = 0.27$); ³primary outcome, n.s. different from questionnaire ($p = 0.27$).

	Assumed	Observed
Prevalence of RBD in PD (by polysomnography)	25% (7 with RBD, 23 without)	81% (13 positive, 3 negative, 8 inconclusive ¹)
RBDSQ sensitivity	96%	100% (n=13 participants)
RBDSQ specificity	56%	33% (n=3 participants)
dBM sensitivity²	Comparable to questionnaire	91% (n=13 participants) ²
dBM specificity³	Higher than questionnaire	0% (n= 3 participants) ³

The availability of only 3 PSG-negative participants in the confirmation cohort precludes reliable judgement of the specificity of the dBM for RBD. If a formal analysis is done with this low number of participants, all criteria noted above will be missed. The consortium is currently evaluating approaches to mitigate this issue in the future. One potential approach could be to increase the number of participants without RBD of the confirmation cohort that can be used for analysis.

4.2 Secondary endpoint - Sensitivity of dBM for RBD

The sensitivity of the screening questionnaire and of the dBM for RBD detection were high (**Table 8**). There was no statistical difference between the performance of the dBM and the RBDSQ.

4.3 Secondary endpoint - Daytime somnolence dBM

With respect to the dBM for daytime somnolence, the secondary outcome assessed whether smartwatch accelerometry-derived mobility features can serve as objective correlates of self-reported daytime sleepiness as measured by the ESS, and whether these associations identified in the development cohort can be reproduced in the confirmation cohort. This secondary endpoint would have been considered positive if at least one predefined feature showed a statistically significant Spearman correlation with ESS ($p < 0.05$) and a coefficient of determination exceeding $r^2 > 0.70$. The development of the dBM for daytime somnolence is described in D3.3.

Overall, the observed associations were small. The highest positive correlations with ESS were found for nap-duration features (e.g., mean_nap_duration_mean, $\rho \approx 0.08$; total_nap_duration_std, $\rho \approx 0.07$; median_nap_duration_mean, $\rho \approx 0.07$), while several related metrics showed near-zero or weak negative correlations (e.g., total_nap_duration_mean, $\rho \approx 0.00$; mean_nap_duration_std, $\rho \approx -0.09$). None of the investigated features approached the pre-specified performance criterion (significant correlation with $p < 0.05$ and $r^2 > 0.70$). Therefore, this secondary endpoint was not met in the confirmation cohort.

4.4 Secondary endpoints - Feasibility for dBM's assessment of bradykinesia, dyskinesias and tremor

Study participants wore a smartwatch throughout the study, which recorded inertial sensor and photoplethysmographic parameters. **Table 9-Table 11** summarize these general features recorded by participants in the two cohorts of the dBM-DEV study. Recordings of the heart rate were used as proxy for the smartwatch being worn on the wrist.

As participants across all cohorts wore the smartwatch during substantial portions of both daytime and night time, this aspect of the feasibility assessment for passive dBM recordings was considered successful. Participants of development cohort were observed for approximately four 4 (weeks), while participants of the confirmation cohort were observed for approximately one to three months. Correlations of accelerometer-derived dBM's with the corresponding clinical scales were evaluated as exploratory endpoints. They are described in section 4.7.

Table 9 Features related to feasibility of bradykinesia, dyskinesias and tremor in the development cohort for participants with RBD

Information	Daytime (07:00-21:59)		Night-time (22:00-06:59)	
	median	range	median	range
Days with smartwatch heartrate data	29	1-49	29	3-50
Hours with smartwatch heartrate data	389	1-580	245	18-361
Hours with smartwatch heartrate data per day	13	4-15	8	3-9
Days with smartwatch accelerometry data	29	3-55	29	3-55
Hours with smartwatch accelerometry data	424	36-792	253	18-467
Hours with smartwatch accelerometry data per day	14.5	7-15	9	4-9

Table 10 Features related to feasibility of bradykinesia, dyskinesias and tremor in the development cohort for participants without RBD (controls)

Information	Daytime (07:00-21:59)		Night-time (22:00-06:59)	
	median	range	median	range
Days with smartwatch heartrate data	29	2-54	29	2-54

Hours with smartwatch heart rate data per day	361	19-676	234	9-435
Hours with smartwatch heartrate data per day	14	10-15	8.1	5-9
Days with smartwatch accelerometry data	29	5-55	29	5-55
Hours with smartwatch accelerometry data	434	60-821	254	36-482
Hours with smartwatch accelerometry data per day	14.3	12-15	8.6	7-9

Table 11 Features related to feasibility of bradykinesia, dyskinesias and tremor in the confirmation cohort

Information	Daytime (07:00-21:59)		Night-time (22:00-06:59)	
	median	range	median	range
Days with smartwatch heartrate data	63	2-123	69	2-123
Hours with smartwatch heart rate data per day	658	1-1,758	490	9-435
Hours with smartwatch heartrate data per day	13	1-15	7	2-9
Days with smartwatch accelerometry data	70	1-123	71	2-124
Hours with smartwatch accelerometry data	983	1-1,823	595	1,086
Hours with smartwatch accelerometry data per day	14	1-15	8.3	2-9

4.5 Secondary endpoint - Feasibility for active test of posture and gait

A Comprehensive Motor Function Test (CMFT) was developed that makes use of motor tasks that were adapted from items of the MDS-UPDRS assessment scale and smartphone camera-based pose tracking. The CMFT was part of the mAI-Health app and combines the associated movements of four MDS-UPDRS III items in a sequence with the following order: right foot stomping (item 3.8R), left foot stomping (item 3.8L), arising from a chair (item 3.9), standing still for 5 s (item 3.13), 3 steps forward (adjusted item 3.10), turn, take 3 steps returning to the chair (adjusted item 3.10). Detailed information and validation results regarding the CMFT can be found in Section 9 of deliverable D3.3.

Sixty-nine (69) CMFT sessions were recorded during the dBM-DEV study from 29 participants (1-6 sessions per participant). To process the CMFT recordings in the dBM-DEV study, an automated movement segmentation methodology was designed to identify the first and last frame of each motor task from the continuous sequence of detected body landmarks as reported in D3.3. Sequences of body landmarks were first resampled to 30 fps by using 1-D cubic spline interpolation, to simulate the body landmark sequences captured in a training set. Then the automated movement segmentation procedure was applied to each sequence. Problems with automated movement segmentation were observed in 40/69 recordings (**Table**

12). To mitigate these problems in the future, the instructions and UI of the CMFT test will be revised.

Table 12 Problems encountered in automated movement segmentation for the CMFT

No. of recordings	Comment
29	Automated segmentation proceeded without problems.
16	Automated segmentation cannot proceed because the two turning points (times) during the gait item are not detected.
20	Automated segmentation cannot proceed because the standing up point (time) cannot be detected.
4	Automated segmentation cannot proceed because the start-walking point (time) cannot be detected. However, in this case, items 3.8, 3.9 and 3.13 have been correctly processed.

4.6 Secondary endpoint - Feasibility for active tests of cognitive performance

Participants were asked to perform active tests of cognitive performance within the mAI-Health app every two weeks throughout the dBM-DEV study. The following tests were used: a working memory test (N-Back task), the Balloon Analogue Risk Task (BART), and the Stop-Signal task (see D3.3 for details).

To assess feasibility of these smartphone-based cognitive active testing, we quantified adherence as the number of completed cognitive testing sessions per cohort (**Table 13**). Across cohorts, completion of at least one session was common, supporting the feasibility of repeated remote cognitive assessments. Some attrition was observed during the study for all cohorts, but the extent of attrition was within the range observed in the literature², i.e., median retention in the study of 5 days. Correlation of test performance with the clinical score (MoCA) at baseline was conducted as an exploratory endpoint and is discussed in section 4.7.

Table 13 Adherence to cognitive testing by cohort (≥ 1 to ≥ 6 completed sessions), n (%). Note that the study duration for the first two cohorts was shorter than for the confirmation cohort.

Completed Sessions	≥ 1	≥ 2	≥ 3	≥ 4	≥ 5	≥ 6
dBM-DEV study cohort						
Development-RBD (DEV-RBD)	19 (63.3%)	12 (40.0%)	-	-	-	-
Development-control (DEV-Control)	17 (70.8%)	13 (54.2%)	-	-	-	-
Confirmation	22 (78.6%)	21 (75.0%)	17 (60.7%)	15 (53.6%)	7 (25.0%)	5 (17.9%)

² Pratap, A., Neto, E. C., Snyder, P., Stepnowsky, C., Elhadad, N., Grant, D., ... & Omberg, L. (2020). Indicators of retention in remote digital health studies: a cross-study evaluation of 100,000 participants. NPJ digital medicine, 3(1), 21.

4.7 Exploratory endpoints - Correlation between motor symptom dBM and clinical scores

The development of all dBM is described in deliverable D3.3. dBM for rest tremor, upper limb slowness of movement and dyskinesias were based on accelerometer data from the smartwatch. dBM for slowness of fine (finger) movement are based on touchscreen typing sessions. dBM for cognitive function are based on the active tests listed in the previous section.

4.7.1 Smartwatch-based assessment of rest tremor

In the dBM-DEV dataset (81 subjects: 28 PD, 29 RBD, 24 healthy controls; data exported January 29, 2025). Three subjects were excluded: 1 RBD subject due to missing accelerometer files and 2 subjects (1 RBD and 1 PD) with insufficient accelerometer data. The PD subsample showed rest tremor with mean \pm SD of 0.86 ± 1.08 points in the clinical rating scale (MDS-UPDRS items 3.17a/b, dominant wrist). The maximum score was 4 points, so this value corresponds to a low prevalence of tremor in this group of participants. Participants with iRBD and healthy controls showed no tremor (0.00 ± 0.00). Daily rest tremor severity predictions were derived by aggregating window-level predictions.

Correlation of accelerometry features with the corresponding clinical scores (MDS-UPDRS item 3.17) demonstrated strong alignment, with tremor amplitude correlating at $\rho = 0.62$ ($p < 0.005$) and tremor constancy at $\rho = 0.42$ ($p < 0.005$), supporting robustness under real-world, free-living conditions.

4.7.2 Smartwatch-based assessment of dyskinesias

In the dBM-DEV dataset (81 subjects: 28 PD, 29 RBD, 24 healthy controls; data exported January 29, 2025), three subjects were excluded: 1 RBD subject due to missing accelerometer files and 2 subjects (1 RBD and 1 PD) with insufficient accelerometer data. The dBM-DEV study provides per-subject MDS-UPDRS Part IV.1 dyskinesia scores (% awake hours with dyskinesia) rather than task-level binary annotations, representing a different annotation paradigm from MJFF-LRS training data. This paradigm mismatch—from task-level binary labels under controlled conditions to subject-level continuous severity from free-living self-report—introduces inherent challenges in cross-paradigm generalization. Among the PD subsample, dyskinesia was highly imbalanced: 21 subjects reported no dyskinesia, and 7 subjects exhibited dyskinesia. The distribution in dyskinesia-affected subjects ranged from slight (1–25% awake hours, $n=5$) to moderate (51–75% awake hours, $n=1$) and severe (76–100% awake hours, $n=1$). All RBD and healthy control participants exhibited no dyskinesias.

A weak but statistically significant correlation of the dBM with the corresponding clinical score (MDS-UPDRS item 4.1) was observed (Spearman $\rho = 0.21$, $p < 0.05$).

4.7.3 Smartwatch-based assessment of slowness of gross upper limb movement

To assess gross upper limb slowness of movement, we developed a multi-stage pipeline using accelerometer data from the Verily Study Watch dataset (146 PD, 32 HCs, and 136 individuals at risk) captured in conditions of daily living for six days following an MDS-UPDRS assessment ($n=633$ assessments). The pipeline predicts a composite score (dBM) of MDS-UPDRS Part III items 3.3 (Rigidity), 3.6 (Pronation-Supination movements of hands), and 3.14 (Global spontaneity of movement (Body bradykinesia)).

The model was tested on the dBM-DEV accelerometer data of both the development and confirmation cohorts. From the dataset (81 subjects: 28 PD, 29 RBD, 24 healthy controls; data exported January 29, 2025), four participants with insufficient accelerometer data were excluded. The model generalised well (Spearman's $\rho=0.61$, $p < 0.05$) despite the use of a

different smartwatch device and the fact that study participants had milder symptoms than the training set. Additional exploratory analysis of the dBM-DEV dataset revealed distinct diurnal patterns and longitudinal trajectories for the development and confirmation cohorts (see D3.3).

4.7.4 Touchscreen typing-based passive assessment of slowness of fine movement

dBMs for slowness of fine (finger) movement were developed by analysing keystroke dynamics from touchscreen typing. Two regressor models were trained with features of key hold time and flight time sequences from the i-PROGNOSIS dataset (Section 8, D3.1) to predict UPDRS Part III Item 23 (Finger Tapping) and Item 22 (Rigidity), respectively. The models were evaluated on data from typing sessions collected in the dBM-DEV study. Each model generated a score for each typing session. For the primary analysis, a participant's median score from all their typing sessions was correlated with clinical labels; for longitudinal score reliability, the reliability of increasing weekly aggregated scores was assessed using intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC).

Within the dBM-DEV study, 12 participants consented to use the virtual keyboard, resulting in 2,147 typing sessions. Although this measure differs from the protocol-specified metrics (hours of use per day), the observed number of sessions suggests good adherence. The digital score for the MDS-UPDRS Part III Finger Tapping item (Item 3.6) showed a good, significant correlation with its clinical label (Spearman's $\rho = 0.65$, $p < 0.05$). The keystroke features for this model demonstrated significant discriminatory power between symptom severity levels. The model exhibited excellent short-term reliability ($ICC > 0.9$) with good reliability ($ICC > 0.75$) across larger time periods. In contrast, the digital score for the Rigidity (Item 3.3) model showed no significant association, likely due to a lack of participants exhibiting rigidity in the cohort. Longitudinal trajectories of the Finger Tapping score were stable over the observation period.

4.7.5 Smartphone-based active tests for cognition

We examined whether digital cognitive task outcomes were associated with baseline cognitive performance as captured by the MoCA. Spearman rank correlations between MoCA and individual task-derived metrics were consistently small ($|\rho| \leq 0.21$). Hence, the predefined exploratory endpoint of $\rho > 0.70$ was not met. The largest absolute association was observed for Stop-Signal mean go reaction time ($\rho = -0.21$), followed by Stop-Signal total correct ($\rho = -0.16$) and BART corrected total ($\rho = -0.16$). Associations for the remaining metrics were weaker (e.g., N-Back reaction time at load 1: $\rho = 0.15$; Stop-Signal correct go: $\rho = -0.15$; BART didBurst: $\rho = -0.10$; BART changeAfterBurst: $\rho = 0.10$; BART corrected pumps: $\rho = -0.10$; Stop-Signal correct stop: $\rho = 0.10$).

We note, however, that the median score of the MoCA was high (28 points) and the range was small (24-30 points), which results from the inclusion criterion that study participants need to be cognitively unimpaired. In addition, the three active tasks are designed to probe specific cognitive domains (e.g., inhibitory control, working memory, and decision-making/risk behavior) rather than global cognitive ability captured by a broad screening measure. Therefore, collecting these task-specific outcomes remains meaningful, as they provide complementary information beyond overall cognitive performance. Differences in task performance across the two cohorts are explored in more detail in deliverable D3.3.

4.8 Corrections for age and sex

Correcting all analyses for age and sex was defined as exploratory endpoint but was not performed by the time of this report; this is a noted limitation. A detailed analysis of the effect of age and sex on the study endpoints will be carried out in the future.

5 Ethical and Personal Data Protection Compliance (GDPR)

The dBM-DEV study was conducted in full compliance with the approved Study Protocol and the applicable EU data protection framework, including Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation – GDPR). The Study Protocol incorporates the required data protection safeguards and was implemented consistently across all participating clinical sites.

The study involves the processing of special categories of personal data, namely health data derived from wearable devices, smartphone-based assessments, and clinical evaluations. Such processing was carried out exclusively for scientific research purposes and based on explicit informed consent obtained from all participants, in accordance with the applicable legal and ethical requirements.

All data collection and analysis activities were performed strictly in accordance with the approved protocol and based on duly obtained informed consent from all study participants. No deviations from the applicable regulatory framework or from the approved Study Protocol were identified.

During participant enrolment, each clinical site carried out structured onboarding procedures. Participants were provided with the relevant informed consent documentation in their native language or, where appropriate, in English. They were duly informed about the objectives of the study, the scope of their participation, and the processing of their personal data for research purposes.

Following enrolment, data were collected via the wearable devices and/or the platform. Data transmissions were performed using encrypted communication channels and securely transferred to a trusted cloud provider (Hetzner). Access to stored data is restricted to specifically authorized personnel and governed by role-based access control mechanisms.

When data are made available to project partners for analysis, pseudonymisation measures are systematically applied. Direct personal identifiers remain exclusively with the clinical sites and are retained only for the period required under the applicable national legal framework. Project partners access solely pseudonymised datasets, ensuring compliance with the principles of data minimisation, integrity and confidentiality. All the above safeguards and processing operations are comprehensively described in the Data Processing Agreement (DPA) signed by all involved partners.

Overall, the dBM-DEV Study demonstrates alignment with EU data protection standards and ethical requirements applicable to clinical research involving digital health technologies.

6 Summary of endpoints

The results of secondary endpoints at this point are summarised in **Error! Reference source not found.** Five out of seven endpoints are considered positive and set in bold. The results of exploratory endpoints are summarised in **Error! Reference source not found.** Four out of five exploratory endpoints were met, again set in bold.

Table 14 Summary of results for secondary endpoints

Secondary endpoint	Result
Sensitivity of the dBM for RBD	Not statistically different from RBDSQ

Correlation of dBM for daytime somnolence with the clinical score (ESS)	Correlations were not statistically significant.
Feasibility of dBMs for bradykinesia, dyskinesias and tremor	Smartwatch data was recorded for much of the hours of a day and for most of the days in the study, so dBM assessment is feasible.
Feasibility of typing-based assessment of fine movement	High number of typing sessions suggests good adherence and feasibility.
Feasibility of dBMs for posture and gait	Problems with pose tracking and movement segmentation were observed in 40/69 recordings. Mitigation strategies are being developed.
Feasibility of dBMs for cognition	At least one test was completed by each participant; attrition over the study duration was acceptable.

Table 15 Summary of results for exploratory endpoints

Exploratory endpoint	Result
Correlation of the dBM for tremor with the clinical score	Good correlation, $\rho = 0.62$ ($p < 0.005$) for tremor amplitude and medium correlation $\rho = 0.42$ ($p < 0.005$) for tremor constancy
Correlation of the dBM for dyskinesias with the clinical score	Weak but statistically significant correlation, $\rho = 0.21$ ($p < 0.05$)
Correlation of the dBM for gross upper limb movement with the clinical score	Good correlation, $\rho = 0.61$ ($p < 0.05$)
Correlation of typing-based movement with clinical score	Good correlation, $\rho = 0.65$ ($p < 0.05$)
Correlation of cognitive tests with clinical score (MoCA)	Small correlations, $ \rho \leq 0.21$

7 Conclusions

The dBM-DEV study enrolled 53 participants in the development cohort (27 with iRBD, 2 with RBD and PD, 24 controls) and 28 participants in the confirmation cohort (all with PD). That is, the remaining clinical sites managed to almost completely compensate for the discontinuation of the partner KCL. The consortium decided against a longer recruitment to not jeopardize overall project timelines. Data monitoring and analysis will continue beyond February 2026.

The primary study end point was to assess specificity of the developed dBMs for RBD. Assessments of specificity requires analysis of participants without RBD. Yet the prevalence of RBD in our cohort of patients with PD was much higher than anticipated (anticipated: 25%, observed by PSG: 81%). The analysis of the primary endpoint is therefore inconclusive at this point. Results of this study will be used to adequately address this issue in future research.

From a scientific point of view, the observed high prevalence of RBD in participants with PD, is interesting because RBD has been used to define subtypes of PD with different prognosis. RBD assessment by the gold standard PSG is based on the analysis of a single night, but the rate of RBD detection increases with the number of nights included in the analysis. This finding therefore indicates that analysis of several nights will be required for accurate determination

of PD subtypes in an individual patient. We anticipate that the dBM will be quite suitable solution to this end.

Appendix – Supplementary documents

The following documents are collated to this report.

S.1 dBM-DEV Study Protocol (version 1.5)

S.2 Ethics approval of study protocol version 1.5 (FIN)

S.3 Ethics approval of study protocol version 2.0 (CHUT)

S.4 Documentation of Corrective and Preventive Action (CAPA)

S.5 Study Data Management Plan (Study DMP)